

Using bio diesel from biomass as an alternative vehicle fuel to reduce China's carbon footprint

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Abstract

CO₂ emission is a burning issue in current time. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the critical anthropogenic greenhouse gas due to its abundance and its ability to remain in the atmosphere for thousands of years ^[1]. It is well-known that CO₂ emissions contribute to global warming and climate change, which can significantly cause severe impacts and consequences for humans and the environment. CO₂ emissions act like a blanket in the air, trapping heat in the atmosphere, and warming up the Earth ^[2]. This layer prevents the Earth from cooling, and thus raises global temperatures.

A typical passenger vehicle emits about 4.6 metric tons of carbon dioxide per year. This assumes the average gasoline vehicle on the road today has a fuel economy of about 22.0 miles per gallon and drives around 11,500 miles per year. Every gallon of gasoline burned creates about 8,887 grams of CO₂.

Biodiesel is a domestically produced, clean-burning, renewable substitute for petroleum diesel. Using biodiesel as a vehicle fuel increases energy security, improves air quality and the environment, and provides safety benefits.

In this paper we will discuss about current carbon emission in china, overview of biomass and their past and present uses, production process of bio diesel from biomass, Limitation of using biodiesel and proposed solution to overcome these challenges.

Keyword: Biomass, Biofuel, Carbon emission, Sustainability

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1 Introduction

There is a wide consensus that human beings have been tackled with great challenges to survive climate change and global warming affairs. Convey sector plays a vital role in the energy structure, oil demand, and CO₂ excretions. In 2010 convey accorded 22% to global CO₂ excretions [3].

New data from world-renowned researchers reveal that state-owned and multinational firms are driving the climate emergency that threatens the future of humanity, and details how they have continued to expand their operations despite being aware of the industry's devastating impact on the planet.

The top 20 oil gas production companies have contributed to 35% of all energy-related carbon dioxide and methane worldwide, totaling 480bn tons of carbon dioxide equivalent (GtCO₂) since 1965. Those identified range from investor-owned firm's household names such as Chevron, Exxon, BP and Shell to state-owned companies including Saudi Aramco and Gazprom.

Chevron topped the list of the eight investor-owned corporations followed closely by Exxon, BP, and Shell. Together these four global businesses are behind more than 10% of the world's carbon emissions since 1965.

Twelve of the top 20 companies are state-owned and together their extractions are responsible for 20% of total emissions in the same period. The leading state-owned polluter is Saudi Aramco, which has produced 4.38% of the global total on its own.

Fig. 1. The top 20 companies on the list have contributed to 35% of all energy-related carbon dioxide and methane worldwide, totaling 480bn tons of carbon dioxide equivalents (GtCO₂e) since 1965.

The global polluter's list uses company-reported annual production of oil, natural gas, and coal and then calculates how much of the carbon and methane in the produced fuels is emitted to the atmosphere throughout the supply chain, from extraction to end use.

It found that 90% of the emissions attributed to the top 20 climate polluters were from the use of their products, such as petrol, jet fuel, natural gas, and thermal coal. One-tenth came from extracting, refining, and delivering the finished fuels.

Fig. 2. Top 20 companies and their global emissions

As the largest appearing country and the world's most congested nation, China has encountered a boost in convey sector and this trend is likely to keep on due to the expectable strong orders. At the same time, the oil import dominion in China was nearly 59% in 2012 ^[4] indicating a latent threat to its energy security. Decarbonizing the transport sector is a quite fundamental challenge and it can be buckled through numerous approaches.

As one of the decarbonization alternatives Biofuels derived from Biomass have the possibility of lowering the use of fossil fuels and CO₂ emissions. Biofuels derived from biomass, such as plants or organic waste, have the potential to reduce both the world's reliance on oil and CO₂ emissions. Because the plants used to make these biofuels use CO₂ as they grow, they have the potential to reduce CO₂ emissions ^[5]. Biofuels and bio-products generated from plant biomass would help to mitigate global warming. This is perhaps due to the CO₂ released during combustion equals the CO₂ tied up by the plant during photosynthesis, leading to no increase in net CO₂ in the atmosphere. Biofuel and bio-product production can generate new income and job opportunities in rural areas. The twenty-first century anticipates a shift to alternative industrial feedstock and green processes for producing these chemicals from renewable

biomass resources [6]. Biomass can be converted to biogas via precise thermal, biological, bodily, chemical, and gasification processes. Because of their advantages in storage, transportation, and flexibility in application, biomass to energy conversion techniques have piqued the interest of more people in producing biofuel [7].

Nowadays, most of the biofuels are produced in the USA (mainly corn ethanol) and Brazil (mainly sugarcane ethanol) (Fig. 3)

Fig. 3. World biofuel production trend.(Source: FAPRI, U.S and World agricultural outlook, 2008.)

Biofuels can be normally divided into standard biofuel and advanced biofuel. The foregoing includes sugar and starch-based ethanol, oil crop-based biodiesel, and direct vegetable oil, as well as biogas obtained through anaerobic dissolution, while the latter mostly include cellulose-based ethanol, biomass-to liquids (BtL)-diesel and biosynthetic gas (bio-SG)[8]. Research on biofuels mainly revolves around the resource perspective and distribution [9], technology happenings [10,11] cost and order [12,13] life cycle excretions [14,15] and food dependability. Mainly speaking, the evolution of biofuels should correlate with the relationship among food dependability, grassland availability, biodiversity, and energy renewability. In China, starch-based ethanol and trans-esterification biodiesel are already economically accessible,

2 Motivation

Transportation accounts for nearly one-third of the total energy consumed worldwide and, unlike other sectors, it relies almost exclusively (96%) on petroleum. From a technical point of view, this high reliance on petroleum is perfectly understandable, since this resource provides compounds (i.e., hydrocarbons) with a number of properties (e.g., high energy density, high chemical stability, low viscosity, and clean burning) that make them excellent fuels. However, the mobility of goods and people, indispensable for the healthy economic development of any society, necessitates an important environmental price. Thus, the vigorous and fast-growing transportation sector is responsible for approximately one-fifth of the greenhouse gas emissions released into the atmosphere every year^[16]. The reduction of these emissions inevitably leads to the utilization of liquid fuels from sources other than petroleum with biomass being the only renewable source of carbon available today.

3 CO₂ emissions in China

Roughly 50% of Chinese CO₂ emissions are from the industrial sector, 40% are from the power sector and 8% are from the transport sector. This sectorial composition of emissions is very different than in most developed countries. In the United States, for example, roughly 22% of heat-trapping gas emissions come from the industrial sector, 28% from the power sector and 29% from the transport sector.

Fig. 4. CO₂ emissions from different sectors^[17]

3.1 Fastest growth of emissions in China

In the first quarter of 2021, China’s CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and cement production grew by 14.5%, relative to the same period a year earlier.

This is shown by the red column in the chart, below. Changes for previous quarters are in blue, highlighting the impact of corona-virus lock downs in the first quarter of 2020.

Fig. 5. Year-on-year change in China’s quarterly CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and cement %. Emissions are estimated from National Bureau of Statistics data on production of different fuels and cement, China Customs data on imports and exports and WIND Information data on changes in inventories, applying IPCC default emissions factors and annual emissions factors per tonne of cement production until 2018. Monthly values are scaled to annual data on fuel consumption in annual Statistical Communication and National Energy Administration data on coal and fossil gas consumption in the first quarter of 2021. Chart by Carbon Brief using High charts ^[18]

This estimate of quarterly emissions growth is consistent with, but somewhat lower than figures published recently by the independent Carbon Monitor academic research group, which provides estimates of “real-time” emissions data.

Even against the pre-pandemic first quarter of 2019, January-March 2021 posted growth of 9%, showing that the increase this year is not only a rebound from the impact of lock downs in 2020.

The latest increase helped push China’s emissions to a new record high of nearly 12Gt CO₂ in the 12 months to March 2021, as shown in the chart below. This is nearly 600Mt CO₂ (5%) higher than the total in 2019, which was unaffected by the corona-virus pandemic.

Fig. 6. Annualized Chinese CO₂ emissions from fossil fuels and cement by source, since 2010, millions of tonnes per year. Emissions are estimated from National Bureau of Statistics data on production of different fuels and cement China Customs data on imports and exports and WIND Information data on changes in inventories applying IPCC default emissions factors and annual emissions factors per tonne of cement production until 2018. Monthly values are scaled to annual data on fuel consumption in annual Statistical Communication and National Energy Administration data on coal and fossil gas consumption in the first quarter of 2021. Chart by Carbon Brief using High charts ^[18].

Emissions in the year to March 2021 grew by nearly 7% year-on-year and by 10% relative to the year to March 2019 respectively, the fastest rates since 2012 and 2013. The reasons for such rapid emissions growth in China relate to the way the country has come out of the corona virus pandemic on a wave of stimulus spending. As Covid-19 lock-downs skew the baseline for year-on-year comparisons, however, this section will be comparing 2021 data to the corresponding periods in 2019.

This follows the practice of most current official statistical reporting and analysis in China. On this basis, around 70% of the increase in emissions in the first quarter of 2021 was due to increased use of coal, with growth in oil demand contributing 20% and fossil gas demand 10%.

These figures are based on data on apparent coal and gas demand, and oil production and imports from the National Energy Administration and WIND Information.

3.2 Explosive increase of vehicles and caused air pollution

With the rapid development of Chinese economy and significant increases in traffic networks, the number of vehicles has grown at an alarming rate. Annual sales of on-road vehicles have grown from roughly 13.64 million in 2009 to 28 million in 2016 (Chinese Automotive Technology & Research Centre, 2017). The growth rate in 2002 and 2009 reached 37.1% and 45.4%, respectively (Chinese Automotive Technology & Research Centre, 2015). The former increase occurred due to China's inclusion in the World Trade Organization (WTO), and purchasing a car is no longer unrealistic due to increased income, particularly in the city middle class. In the 2008 world financial crisis, China's economy was less affected than many other countries. Moreover, China's State Council took effective measures to stimulate domestic demand and consumption, and the automobile industry was augmented rapidly. In 2014, China's automobile productions and sales reached over 23 million and ranked the first place in the world afterward.

Fig. 7. Statistics of annual sales of on-road vehicles in China

3.3 Carbon emissions from transport sector in china

To reveal the CO₂ emissions from the Chinese transportation sector in a more intuitive manner picture 1 and 2 were constructed which depict the spatial changes in the CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector of China from 1997 to 2016 and those from the various provincial transportation sectors, respectively. Picture 2 shows that the CO₂ emissions from the provincial transportation sectors in China have generally increased from 1997 to 2016. The transportation sector has high CO₂ emissions, especially in the more economically developed coastal areas, such as Shanghai, Guangdong, and Jiangsu. The high emissions in these coastal areas may be related to the economic development there and the improvement of transportation infrastructure. Internal and external economic activities are more frequent in these regions. Since regional economic exchanges and interactions are intensive in these regions and demand for the transportation sector is higher in these regions than others their CO₂ emissions are high picture 3 reveals that with the rapid economic and social development the demand for transportation, the energy consumption of the transportation sector and its CO₂ emissions are all increasing.

Fig. 8. Spatial change in the CO₂ emissions from the Chinese transportation sector from 1997 to 2016.^[19]

The CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector in the provinces of China are generally increasing. Therefore, to more clearly characterize the spatial CO₂ emissions changes, the CO₂ emissions data of each province are normalized and mapped using ArcGIS software. Picture 1

reveals that among the provinces, those in the coastal areas have the highest CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector; these levels have remained largely stable over time, with high emissions tending to spread inland. Picture 1 also shows that the overall CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector in China are low. High-emission areas are gradually moving south; i.e., the number of southern areas with high CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector is gradually increasing. Forty years after the reform and opening up the economic development of the southern provinces has gradually surpassed that of the northern provinces. This rapid economic development has also driven the rapid development of the transportation sector and its CO₂ emissions have increased. In particular, within the central provinces, Wuhan has consistently had high CO₂ emissions, which may be related to its advantageous geographical location. The CO₂ emissions from the Sichuan transportation sector in the western transport hub province are also high, which may be associated with national major strategies such as the development of the western region and the implementation of major strategies such as the Belt and Road Initiative. Hence, the demand for the transportation sector has also increased.

Fig. 9. CO₂ emissions from the transportation sector of Chinese provinces in 1997, 2003, 2009, and 2016^[19].

4 An overview of biomass energy

Biomass energy is a large renewable source with the potential for making a significant contribution to the world's energy needs, both environmentally and sustainably. Currently, it contributes between 10 and 14% of the world's primary energy, including about 3% of the world's transport, but with the potential to contribute up to 30–40+% in 2050, depending on the source. Biomass energy has many energy, environmental and socio-economic benefits, both modern and traditional, from electricity and heating to transportation.

4.1 Definition of Biomass

Biomass is any organic matter such as wood, crops, seaweed, animal wastes which can be used as an energy source. Biomass is probably our oldest source of energy after the sun. For thousands of years, people have burned wood to heat their homes and cook their food. Biomass gets its energy from the sun. All organic matter contains stored energy from the sun. During a process called photosynthesis, sunlight gives plants the energy they need to convert water and carbon dioxide into oxygen and sugars. These sugars called carbohydrates, supply plants and the animals that eat plants with energy. Foods rich in carbohydrates are a good source of energy for the human body. Biomass is a renewable energy source because its supplies are not limited. We can always grow trees and crops, and waste will always exist.

4.2 Types of Biomass

- ❖ wood and woody materials;
- ❖ Herbaceous and other annual growth materials such as straws, grasses, leaves, herbaceous energy crops, short rotation woody crops;
- ❖ Agricultural and forestall by-products and residues including shells, hulls, pits.

The majority of biomass sources are represented by wood and wood wastes and by agricultural and forestal wastes: in some countries, forest residues represent more than 70% of the potential of dry biomass ^[20]. The organic material derived from animals is also referred to as biomass. The fourth category of biomass is represented by refuse-derived fuels (RDF) from municipal solid waste (MSW) and non-recyclable papers. The class of MSW is often excluded from the category of biomass, but the origin, except for mixed plastics, is appropriate for inclusion as a biomass type ^[21,22]. Some papers like ^[23] discuss the properties of biomass, important for the

design and development of combustion and other types of energy conversion systems. The main selection criteria for biomass species are growth rate, ease of management, harvesting, and other intrinsic properties, such as moisture/ash/alkali content. Regarding the intrinsic properties, it is important to underline that biomass is mainly made up of carbon. That makes it looked at with great attention among the alternative fuels: it can be either directly used as fuel to produce energy or be turned into liquid or gaseous fuels.

4.3 Use of Biomass

Until the mid-1800s, wood gave Americans 90 percent of the energy used in the country. In 2016, biomass provided 4.89 percent of the total energy we consumed. Biomass has largely been replaced by coal, natural gas, and petroleum. A little less than 42 percent of the biomass used today comes from burning wood and wood scraps such as saw dust. About 48 percent is from biofuels, principally ethanol, that are used as a gasoline additive. The rest comes from crops, garbage, and landfill gas. Industry is the biggest user of biomass. Over 48 percent of biomass is used by industry. Electric utilities use almost 11 percent of biomass for power generation. In turn biomass produces 1.55 percent of the electricity we use. Transportation is the next biggest user of biomass; about 30 percent of biomass is used by the transportation sector to produce biofuels like ethanol and biodiesel. The residential sector uses almost 8 percent of the biomass supply. The most recently reported data showed about three percent of American homes use wood as the only source of heat.

4.3.1 Using Biomass Energy

Usually we burn wood and use its energy for heating. Burning, however, is not the only way to convert biomass energy into a usable energy source. There are four ways:

- **Fermentation:** There are several types of processes that can produce an alcohol (ethanol) from various plants especially corn. The two most commonly used processes involve using yeast to ferment the starch in the plant to produce ethanol. One of the newest processes involves using enzymes to break down the cellulose in the plant fibers, allowing more ethanol to be made from each plant, because all of the plant tissue is utilized not just the starch.
- **Burning:** We can burn biomass in waste-to-energy plants to produce steam for making electricity, or we can burn it to provide heat for industries and homes.

- **Bacterial Decay:** Bacteria feed on dead plants and animals, producing methane. Methane is produced whenever organic material decays. Methane is the main ingredient in natural gas, the gas sold by natural gas utilities. Many landfills are recovering and using the methane gas produced by the garbage.
- **Conversion:** Biomass can be converted into gas or liquid fuels by using chemicals or heat. In India, cow manure is converted to methane gas to produce electricity. Methane gas can also be converted to methanol, a type of alcohol made from fermenting wood. Methane and methanol each have only one carbon atom.

4.3.2 Traditional versus modern applications

As indicated above bio energy has historically been associated with traditional applications such as cooking, lighting, small cottage industries, etc., but with extremely low energy efficiency resulting in huge waste and significant negative environmental impacts. The efficiency of traditional bioenergy use in developing countries (DLCs) varies greatly ranging between 2 and 20%. This compares to 65-80% (or even 90%) when modern technologies are used, particularly in industrial countries like Austria, Finland and Sweden.^[24] Hence, all biomass energy sources must be modernized.

Table 1. Supply potentials of biomass energy resource categories by 2050

Biomass resource category	Supply potential (2050), EJ/year
1 Forest residues: residues from silvicultural thinning and logging; wood processing residues such as sawdust, bark and black liquor; dead wood from natural disturbances, such as storms and insect outbreaks (irregular source). Residue removal rates need to be controlled considering local ecosystem including biodiversity, climate, topography and soil factors. ILUC affects are mostly negligible but may arise if earlier uses are displaced or if soil productivity losses require compensating production. There is a near-term trade-off in that organic matter retains organic C for longer if they are left on the ground instead of being used for energy.	ASIA 3–7 LAM 1–4 MAF 1–3 OECD90 7–20 REF 2–5 Global 17–35

<p>2 Unutilized forest growth: the part of sustainable harvest levels (often set equal to net annual increment) in forests judged as being available for wood extraction, which is above the projected biomass demand for producing other forest products. Includes both biomass suitable for pulp and paper production and biomass that is not traditionally used. The resource potential and mitigation benefit depend (besides fossil C displacement efficiency) on both environmental and socio-economic factors: the change in forest management and harvesting regimes due to bioenergy demand depends on forest ownership and the structure of the associated forest industry; and the forest productivity and C stock response to changes in forest management and harvesting depend on the character of the forest ecosystem, as shaped by historic forest management and events such as fires, storms and insect outbreaks. Forest biomass (sum of categories 1 and 2</p>	<p>ASIA 1 LAM 22 MAF 2 OECD90 33 REF 7 Global 64–74 SRREN 0–110</p>
<p>3 Agriculture residues: manure (given separately in parentheses and not included in the agriculture residue potential); harvest residues (e.g. straw); processing residues (e.g. rice husks from rice milling). Similar environmental restrictions on harvest residue removal as for forests. ILUC effects and timing of C flows also similar, although the longer-term soil C trade-off may be less than previously believed. Residues have varying collection and processing costs (in both agriculture and forestry) depending on quality and how dispersed they are, with secondary residues often having the benefits of not being</p>	<p>ASIA (14) 7–30 LAM (8) 2–11 MAF (6) 3–15 OECD90 (9) 7–13 REF (3) 3 Global (40) 28–59 SRREN (5–50) 15–70</p>

<p>dispersed and having relatively constant quality. Densification and storage technologies would enable cost-effective collections over larger areas</p>	
<p>4 Dedicated biomass plantations: including annual (cereals, oil and sugar crops) and perennial plants (e.g. switchgrass, Miscanthus) and tree plantations (both coppice and single-stem plantations, e.g. willow, poplar, eucalyptus, pine). Higher-end estimates presume favourable agriculture development concerning land use efficiency – especially for livestock production – releasing agriculture lands for bioenergy. Diets are a critical determinant, given the large land requirements to support livestock production. Large areas presently under forests are biophysically suitable for bioenergy plantations but such lands are commonly not considered available due to greenhouse gas (GHG), biodiversity and other impacts. Grasslands and marginal/degraded lands (uncertain extent and suitability) are commonly considered as available for bioenergy, but their use requires careful planning and crop selection to avoid negative impacts concerning GHG balances, water availability, biodiversity and subsistence farming and equity</p>	<p>ASIA 6–144 LAM 7–120 MAF 4–152 OECD90 6–140 REF 3–136 Global 26–675 SRREN 0–700 .</p>
<p>5 Organic wastes: waste from households and restaurants, discarded wood products such as paper and demolition wood, and wastewaters suitable for anaerobic biogas production. Organic waste may be dispersed and also heterogeneous in quality but the health and environmental gains from collection and proper</p>	<p>ASIA 4–7 LAM 2–3 MAF 2–3 OECD90 2–3 REF 0–1 Global 10–17 SRREN 5– >50</p>

<p>management through combustion or anaerobic digestion can be significant. Also must consider whether the waste had an alternative use that will need to be met from some other source.</p>	
<p>Total potential: the total global and regional potentials are obtained by summing the average potentials for the different categories and then rounding to the nearest 10. This approach implies averaging over a wide range of contrasting assumptions made in the different studies concerning the development for critical parameters discussed in the text. This approach to derive global numbers is sensitive to selection of studies in the sense that including several studies using similar assumptions and models and reaching similar (high or low) potential estimates results in higher weight for these studies. However, the judgement is that the selection includes a representative mix of studies concerning models and modeller views on critical parameters.</p>	<p>ASIA 100 LAM 100 MAF 70 OECD90 140 REF 80 Global 500 SRREN <50– >1,000</p>
<p>Notes: ‘LAM’ – Latin America; ‘MAF’ – Middle East and Africa; ‘OECD90’ – OECD countries in 1990; ‘REF’ – remaining countries. According to Creutzig et al.19 potentials are obtained from studies that project biomass availability for energy based on a ‘food/fiber first principle’ and various restrictions with reference to resource limitations and environmental concerns – but without any cost consideration – to obtain ‘technical’ potentials, as restricted by some sustainability considerations. The global ranges reported in SRREN20, italic numbers in the table, have high upper limits due to a broader set of studies but have fewer restrictions and start with zero for no resource availability for energy. Source: Creutzig et al.19 Quoted in Rosillo-Calle et al.21 pp. 14–15</p>	

Table 2. Bioenergy supply, feedstocks and associated land demand estimates for 2010

	Global production (EJ)	Feedstock	Land occupied (million ha)
Global primary energy	520	Predominantly fossil	Not quantified
Total bioenergy	62	All forms, traditional and modern	≈50
Traditional bioenergy	40	Mostly from residues, wastes and harvesting parts of live trees (pollarding)	Not quantified
Modern bioenergy	21.5		
Biofuels	4.2	Agricultural crops	≈50 <13 ≈30
Heating (domestic and industrial)	13	2/3 residues and wastes, 1/3 energy crops (lignocellulosic)	
Electricity	4.1	50% from energy crops, 50% from residues and wastes	≈10
Source: See Rosillo-Calle and Woods ^[25] for further details			

Modern applications are rapidly replacing traditional uses, particularly in industrialized countries. Many developing countries are also undergoing changes, albeit in varying degrees. For example, in China, the use of traditional biomass energy is declining rapidly while in some areas of India it is increasing. In absolute terms, however, the use of bioenergy is increasing due to rapid population growth, rising energy demand, and a lack of other accessible or affordable alternative energy sources, particularly for the urban and rural poor. Modern

applications necessitate capital, skills, technology, market structure, and a certain level of development, all of which are in short supply in many DLC rural areas [25,26].

As shown in Table 2, traditional biomass sources provided approximately 40 EJ of energy. This is a rough estimate that is almost certainly underestimated because traditional uses are at the core of the informal economy in poor countries and are rarely recorded in official statistics. Traditional sources of bioenergy in the poorest DLCs still represent the bulk of energy use, although this is declining as many economies modernize. For example, biomass accounts for 60-80% of energy in Burundi, Mozambique, Nepal, Rwanda, Sudan, Tanzania, and Uganda.

Proportionally, the general trend is increasing use in industrial countries and a decrease in DLCs, but with important differences. In the industrialized world, the increase is primarily the result of deliberate policies to promote renewable energy, combined with increased energy efficiency and lower growth in energy demand (in all sectors). In the case of DLCs, the overall increase reflects rapid energy demand at all levels, as a result of economic development and low energy, as well as a desire to shift away from traditional bioenergy.

5 Conversion of Biomass in to bio-fuel

Biofuels are receiving tremendous attention worldwide as a source of renewable energy. Biomass, which is plentiful in nature, can be converted into various types of biofuels. Different forms of fuel depend on the type of conversion processes such as acid & alkaline pre-treatment, pyrolysis & gasification method, transesterification, fermentation process, etc., and produce biodiesel, bio-methane, bioethanol, bio-oil, gasoline, etc. Many research articles on biofuel production methods have recently been published. In this chapter, we will attempt to summarize some of them.

Table 3. Biomass feed stock's

1. Forest products	Wood Logging residues Trees, shrubs and wood residues Sawdust, barks, roots, etc.
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2. Bio-renewable wastes	Agricultural wastes Crop residues Mill wood wastes Urban wood wastes Urban organic wastes Municipal solid wastes Domestic solid wastes
3. Energy crops	Short -rotation woody crops Herbaceous woody crops Grasses Starch crops Sugar crops Forage crops Oilseed crops
4. Aquatic plants	Algae Water weed Water hyacinth Reed and rushes
5. Food crops	Grains Oil crops
6. Sugar crops	Sugar cane Sugar beets Molasses Sorghum
7. Landfill	
8. Industrial organic wastes	

Fig.10. Hierarchy of biomass conversion process

5.1 Generation of Biofuel

5.1.1 First Generation Biofuel

First generation biofuel is the threat of limitation in the food supply, which may affect the human world population as the feedstock is derived from food sources. Millions of people worldwide are currently suffering from hunger, malnutrition, and the utilization of food resources as fuel.

Fig.11. First generation biofuel.

5.1.2 Second Generation Biofuel

Non-food agricultural products such as sorghum, tuberous crop, cellulosic biomass, and algae are not available in China for biofuel production. China has rules in place to regulate biofuel production in order to avoid competition with winning agricultural machinery and land used for food production. The following section goes over the most important lignocellulosic feedstock applicants for the bioethanol industry. To date, no feedstock has been designated as the "winner" source; each feedstock has advantages as well as disadvantages^[27]. Taiwan plans to produce approximately 300 million litres of bioethanol and 15 million litres of biodiesel by 2020^[28].

Fig.12. Second generation biofuel.

5.1.3 Third generation biofuel

The conversion technology for utilising microalgae biomass can be classified into two categories: thermochemical and biochemical conversion (similar to terrestrial biomass).

Thermochemical condensation refers to the thermal decomposition of organic components into fuel products, which includes direct combustion, gasification, thermochemical liquefaction, and pyrolysis. Anaerobic digestion, alcoholic fermentation, and photo organic hydrogen production are all biological processes for converting biomass to other fuels [29].

Fig.13. Third generation biofuel.

Fig.14. Fourth generation biofuel [5]

5.2 Composition of Biomass

5.2.1 cellulose

Cellulose is a homopolysaccharide composed of D-glucopyranose devices which are linked by way of β -(1-4)glycosidic bonds with a miles better diploma of polymerization (10,000–150,000) than hemicellulose [30].

Plant biomass contains 40-50% cellulose molecules, which are held together by intermolecular hydrogen bonds in their natural state, but they have a sturdy tendency to form intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen bonds, which increases the rigidity of cellulose and makes it highly insoluble and extremely resistant to most natural solvents. Naturally, cellulose molecules exist as bundles that aggregate in the shape of micro-fibrils, i.e., crystalline and amorphous regions. [7]

Furthermore, cellulose is a high-molecular-weight polymer that makes up the fibers in lignocellulosic materials, and its degradation begins anywhere between 240 and 350 °C due to

the crystalline structure's high resistance to thermal depolymerization, which is due to its strength ^[31].

5.2.2 Hemicellulose

The amorphous shape of hemicelluloses, which is easily hydrolyzed or dissolved in an alkali solution, results from branching. Some researchers believe that herbal bonding may lead to the possibility of adhesive products produced by hemicellulose degradation [12]. Hemicelluloses (C₅H₈O₄)_m are heterogeneously branched biopolymers that contain pentoses (β -Dxylose, α -L- arabinose), hexoses (β -D-mannose, β -D-glucose, α -D galactose), and uronic acids (α -D-glucuronic, α -D-4-O-methylgalacturonic and α -D-galacturonic acids). Because of their amorphous and branched structure (with short lateral chains) as well as their lower molecular weight, they hydrolyze relatively cleanly ^[27].

5.2.3 Lignin

Lignin, the most abundant fragrant polymer, is a three-dimensional amorphous phenolic biopolymer. The biosynthesis of lignin should be considered to arise from the polymerization of three types of phenylpropane units as monolignols: p- coumaryl, sinapyl, and coniferyl alcohols, which allow for the rigid form^[32]. The properties of polydispersity characterize lignin, just as they do hemicellulose. Different branching and bonding are observed in otherwise similar molecules^[29].

Table.4 Compositional data analysis of Biomass.

Sources of Biomass	Cellulose (%)	Hemicellulose (%)	Lignin (%)
Birch angiosperm	44.9	32.7	19.3
Spruce Gymnosperm	46.1	24.6	26.3
Crop residues	30-45	16-27	3-13
Wood residues	45-56	10-25	18-30
Cotton	45-50	14-20	24-28
Jute	40-47	18-25	20-25
Mesta	65-70	10-14	08-10
Sunn hemp	70-92	18-22	03-05
Coir pith	26-30	03-07	30-40
Sugarcane bagasse	26-50	25-28	23-25
Corn cobs	33-37	31-40	06-10
Rice straw	30-40	15-18	09-13
Wheat straw	32-40	20-25	8-14
Lantana camara	30-35	18-25	12-20

Ricinus communis	35–42	15–18	15–20
Bambusa bambos	40–48	12–15	18–25
Saccharum spontaneum	38–45	20–25	15–22
Jatropha curcas	38–45	10–15	08–12
Prosopis juliflora	40–50	15–20	22–30
Water hyacinth	16–20	42–50	03–06
Corncoobs	45	35	15
Barley straw	33-40	20-35	8-17
Corn stover	39-42	22-28	18-22
Parthenium hysterophorus	40–45	18–25	15–22
Nut shells	25-30	25-30	30-40
Empty fruit bunch	41	24	21.2
Switch grass	45	31.4	12

Waste papers from chemical pulps	60-70	10-20	5-10
Organic compound from wastewater solid	8-15	0	0
Paper	85–99	0	0–15
Sunflower shell	48.4	34.6	17
Leaves	15-20	80-85	0
Almond shell	50.7	28.9	20.4
Stored refuse	60	20	20
Cotton seed hairs	80–95	5–20	0
Walnut shell	25.6	22.7	52.3
Miscanthus	24	44	17
Hazelnut shell	28.8	30.4	42.9
Oat straw	31–37	24–29	16–19
Bamboo	26–43	15–26	21–31
Sorghum straw	32-35	24-27	15-21
Rye straw	33–35	27–30	16–19
Coastal Bermuda grass	25	35.7	6.4
Banana waste	13.2	14.8	14
Jute fiber	45–53	18–21	21–26
Olive husk	24	23.6	48.4
Deciduous	18–25	40–44	15–35
Willow	25	50	19
Larch	35	26	27

[33] [34][35][36]

Fig.15. Compositional analysis of biomass feedstocks.

5.3 Pre-treatment

A pretreatment step is performed in the biochemical conversion of biomass to ethanol to reduce the recalcitrance of biomass in order to recognize the excessive yields required for an economically preferred industrial process. Pretreatment can be an effective technique for hydrolyzing the hemicellulose or removing a fragment of the lignin, increasing the accessibility of the remaining cellulose to enzymatic hydrolysis and increasing the rates and extent of enzymatic hydrolysis. Mineral acids are commonly used for pretreatment, such as diluted sulfuric acid at concentrations ranging from 0.22-6% w/w at temperatures ranging from 100-200 C. However, such pretreatment operations generally necessarily require a long and complex residence time, which slows down industrial operations. Chemical pretreatment, in contrast, involves the usage of acid, alkali, natural solvents, and ionic liquids to disrupt the lignin shape of lignocellulosic biomass and boost the inner surface location. The expansion of inner surface proximity might indeed help in enhancing conversion efficiency and product yield [37].

5.3.1 Physical Pretreatment

Physical pretreatment is the mechanical breakdown of lignocellulose biomass. These methods call for the use of cutting, ball, and hammer mills, as well as screw presses and ultrasound. Although the term is still widely used, it is generally understood that almost all feedstocks require some sort of size reduction (e.g., bodily pretreatment) after field harvesting. Physical pretreatment strategies reduce the scale of lignocellulosic biomass to facilitate subsequent treatments. The reduction of biomass size to at least one mm reduces cellulose crystallinity and increases the digestibility of cellulose and hemicellulose inside lignocellulosic biomass [6].

5.3.2 Acid Pretreatment

One of the most widely researched and applied methods is the pretreatment of lignocellulose biomass with dilute acid solutions. According to a 2005 comparative study, dilute sulfuric acid pretreatment is the most economically viable pretreatment method for increasing the conversion of lignocellulose biomass to ethanol^[38]. The effects of dilute sulfuric acid on rice straw containing 36.6% glucose, 16.1% xylose, and 14.9% lignin at various acid concentrations of 0.5-1.0% w/w and instances ranging from 1 to 25 minutes were investigated. Following enzymatic hydrolysis, the study reported a maximum overall sugar yield of 83% under gold standard conditions: 1% w/w sulfuric acid, 1-5 min, at 160-180C. Excessive strain liquid chromatography was used to quantify monomeric sugars, furfural, and 5- hydroxymethyl furfural (HMF) (HPLC). Furfural and HMF are formed via of the degradation of xylose and glucose, respectively, and reduce the ethanol yield. These compounds are commonly referred to as inhibitors because they reduce the efficiency of sugar-liberating enzymes (celluloses) and ethanol-producing yeast. The dilute acid pretreatment became more severe (on the premise of acid awareness, temperature, and time) the inhibitor concentration was observed correspondingly^[39].

5.3.3 Alkaline Pretreatment

Alkaline pretreatment of lignocellulosic materials causes swelling, which leads to decreased crystallinity, increased inner floor area, disruption of the lignin structure, and separation of structural linkages between lignin and carbohydrates^[40]. Alkali pretreatment refers to the application of alkaline solutions such as NaOH, Ca(OH)₂ (lime), or ammonia to extract lignin and part of the hemicelluloses, thereby boosting enzyme accessibility to the cellulose. For the alkaline hydrolysis of the samples three alkaline solution NaOH, Ca(OH)₂ of equal concentration were taken and every lignocellulosic biomasses were treated inside the following way 3g of ground biomass from each crop was placed in a 1000ml Erlenmeyer flask, and 300 ml of 3% (w/v) NaOH solution was delivered to it. The flask becomes cotton plugged and autoclaved at 121°C for 30 min. The material obtained after treatment turned darkish in color, so it became filtered via muslin cloth and washed in walking distilled water until no color became visible within the wash water. The neutralised residue was manually pressed to remove excess water before being used for enzymatic hydrolysis. A portion of the handled biomass was dried in an oven at 70oC for 24 hours and ground to a fine particle size in a Laboratory Mill for compositional evaluation studies^[28].

5.3.4 Transesterification

Animal and vegetable oil are composed of triglycerides, which are esters of three different fatty acids and glycerol. The addition of alcohol and alkali de-polymerizes it during the

transesterification process, making it a stronger nucleophile. It can be seen that the response now only contained triglycerides and alcohol. Under normal conditions, the reaction is very slow, so heating is used to speed up the reaction by using a catalyst (acid/base). Sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, and sodium methoxide are common transesterification catalysts ^[37].

5.3.5 Ultrasonic

Ultrasonic waves drive the response mixture to produce and crumble bubbles uniformly in the ultrasonic reactor methodology. At the same time, cavitation provides the distance for mixing and heating required for the transesterification process. Thus, using an ultrasonic reactor for biodiesel production significantly reduces reaction time, response temperatures, and energy input. Therefore, the technique of transesterification will run in line as opposed to the use of time-ingesting batch processing. Industrial-scale ultrasonic devices enable the industrial-scale processing of many barrels per day ^[37]. Additionally, studies have shown that once sufficient depth is applied for the duration of ultrasonic cell disruption, heat is generated, which can enhance the efficiency of the disruption of biomass cells, that disruption using ultrasonic cavitation is affected by the viscosity and temperature of the liquid media, and that ultracavitation is significantly more extreme at a low frequency of 18-40 Hz than at a high frequency of approximately 400-800 Hz ^[41].

5.4 Thermochemical Method

5.4.1 Gasification

Gasification is a chemical process that converts carbonaceous materials (hydrocarbons) to synthesis gas (syngas) through partial oxidation with air, oxygen, and/or steam at high temperatures, typically in the 800-900°C range. Gasification is a promising method of harnessing this energy source. Producer gas derived from agricultural residues can replace 70-90% of diesel oil in compression ignition engines used in irrigation pump sets, generators, threshers, and crushers. Gasification is the incomplete oxidation of organic compounds after a pyrolysis decomposition step. The oxygen in the oxidizing agent used for gasification (air, oxygen, CO₂ or steam water) reacts with carbon to produce a combustible gas known as "syngas." This syngas consists mainly of carbon monoxide (CO) and hydrogen (H₂), with minor amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂), water (H₂O), methane (CH₄), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), ammonia (NH₃), and, under certain conditions, solid carbon (C), nitrogen (N₂), argon (Ar), and tar traces. Nitrogen and argon are byproducts of the use of air as a reactant or of their use as plasma gas ^[42]. Argon is produced when air is used as a reactant or when it is used as a plasma gas^[42].

Table.5 Types of gasifier & percentage data.

Gasifier Type	Biomass	GA	Gasification Temperature (°C)	Cold Gass Efficiency(%)	Char Conversion (%)	Tar Content (g/Nm ³)
Updraft gasifier	downward	upward	950–1150 (max values) Syngas exit temperature: 150–400	20-60	40-85	1-150
Downdraft gasifier	downward	downward	900–1050 (max value) Syngas exit temperature: 700	30-60	<85	0.015-1.5
Fluidized bed gasifier	upward	upward	800–900	<70	<70	10-40
Circulating fluidized bed gasifier	upward	upward	750–850	50-60	70-95	5-12
Entrained flow gasifier	downward	downward	1300–1500	30-90	60-90	~ =0–0.2

5.4.2 Liquefaction

In all circumstances, the oil yield was higher with catalytic aqueous liquefaction than with non-catalytic aqueous liquefaction. The common oil yield was 31.2% in non-catalytic aqueous liquefaction and 63.7% in catalytic aqueous liquefaction (Table 6). The common char yield becomes 33.5% within the non-catalytic aqueous liquefaction and 33.0% inside the catalytic aqueous liquefaction (Table 6). The difference between common oil yields and average char yields becomes apparent. The oil yield decreased and the char yield increased with both aqueous liquefaction procedures as the lignin content increased.

Table.6 Bio-oil and char yields from non-catalytic and catalytic aqueous liquefaction of biomass samples

Lignin content	Bio-oil content of liquefaction products		Char content of liquefaction products (%)	
	Direct liquefaction	Catalytic liquefaction	Direct liquefaction	Catalytic liquefaction
43.5	27.8	76.9	38.9	19.6
25.2	40.2	88.6	23.6	10.2
22.4	33.8	86.4	22.2	11.8
26.9	29.3	58.7	25.8	37.4
51.0	23.1	43.2	49.0	51.9
15.1	75.8	92.5	21.3	6.0
28.4	25.9	48.1	25.4	47.5
53.0	21.6	40.2	50.5	55.3
54.1	21.0	38.6	44.7	57.7
Average	31.2	63.7	33.5	33.0

The amount of stable residue increased in proportion to the lignin content during the liquefaction process. Lignin is a macromolecule with a complex third-dimensional structure composed of alkylphenols. Unfastened phenoxy radicals are commonly formed by the thermal decomposition of lignin at temperatures above 525 K, and the radicals have a random tendency to form stable residues via condensation or repolymerization. Because of the formation of strong residue as an outcome of repolymerization of heavy oils once produced, the yield of heavy oil decreased as the protecting time turned prolonged^[43].

Fig.16. Separation scheme of liquefaction products from biomass liquefaction

5.4.3 Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is the thermal breakdown of biomass at temperatures ranging from 200°C to 600°C to produce a medium energy gas, a complex pyrolysis oil, and char. Pyrolysis is a vital first step in all biomass gasification and combustion processes: in combustion, subsequent oxidation of the goods results in total heat release; in gasification, the goods are used immediately or transformed to other gasoline forms. Pyrolysis is categorized into two types: slow and fast. When heating costs are low or there is a large amount of biomass present, pyrolysis produces an excessive amount of charcoal, which must then be gasified. At the highest fast heating rates, cellulose is essentially converted to a gas containing a high percentage of olefins, which could be advantageous as a chemical feedstock; char production is minimal [44].

Fig.17. Types of Pyrolysis reactors

5.4.3.1 Pyrolysis process

All pyrolysis reductions have a defined feedstock length for efficient heat transfer and simple operation. Fluidized mattress pyrolysis reactors, for example, typically require particle sizes ranging from 2 to 6 mm. Therefore, biomass must be organized to the desired length through reducing and grinding operations. In addition to sizing, the biomass materials must be dried to a moisture content of less than 10% wt unless a clearly dry straw fabric is available. Drying is critical to avoid the negative effects of water on the pyrolysis product's stability, viscosity, pH, corrosiveness, and other liquid properties ^[45]. The liquid yields can be accelerated by grinding and drying the raw cloth, but the production fees are also increased. In their observation timber biomass dried at temperatures of 200oC and 240oC for 45 and 90 minutes, respectively. Their results imply that increasing the drying temperature increased the yield of pyrolysis products. Char is an intermediate solid residue that is shaped in reactors at some stage during the

pyrolysis process. Char separation must be quick and powerful since that acts as a vapour cracking catalyst and contributes to the formation of polycyclic fragrant hydrocarbons (PAHs) in pyrolysis processes, especially at low temperatures. The three primary products of biomass pyrolysis are char, everlasting gases, and vapours that condense to a dark brown viscous liquid at room temperature. Maximum liquid production occurs at temperatures ranging from 350oC to 500oC [46].

Fig.18. Pyrolysisprocess

Slow pyrolysis yields more charcoal, whereas fast pyrolysis yields 75 wt% liquid bio-oil, 15-25 wt% solid charcoal, and 10-20 wt% non-condensable gases. Flash Pyrolysis, which occurs at around 500 1C with a short vapor house time, produces 95.5% liquid biofuel. Pyrolysis of microalgae has been shown to produce more high-quality bio-oil than lignocellulose pyrolysis [47]. In comparison to other conversion technologies, research on pyrolysis of algal biomass has been extensive and has yielded reliable and promising results that could lead to commercial exploitation. After modifying the metabolic pathway of the microalgae *Chlorella prothothecoides* to promote heterotrophic growth, fast pyrolysis was used to enhance oil yield. The recorded oil yield of 57.9% dry wt. foundation from heterotrophic cultivation (HHV of 41 MJ kg¹) changed into 3. Four times that of phototrophic cultivation, implying that pyrolysis has the capability in algal biomass-to-liquid conversion. Fast pyrolysis of *C. Prothothecoides* and *Microcystis aeruginosa* grown phototrophically yielded bio-oil yields of 18% (HHV of 30 MJ kg⁻¹) and 24% (HHV of 29 MJ kg⁻¹), respectively [48].

Table 7. Different types of pyrolysis process details

Pyrolysis process	Temperature (K)	Heating rates(K/s)	Residence time(s)	Clasification
Slow	(Low) 550-950	(Low) 0.1–1	(High) 45–550	☐ High char formation compared to liquid and gaseous products ☐ Energy intensive due to low heat transfer
Fast	(High) 850–1250	(High) 10–200	(Short) 0.5–10	☐ 60–75 wt% of liquid bio-oil ☐ 15–25 wt% of solid char ☐ 10–20 wt% of non-condensable gases Most preferred method: low investment cost and high energy efficiencies
Flash	(Very High) 1050–1300	(Very high) >1000	(Very short) <0.5	☐ Currently at pilot stage ☐ Bio-oil yield of 75%

5.4.4 Torrefaction

Torrefaction is a thermochemical pretreatment system at 200-300 degrees Celsius in an inert environment that converts biomass into a relatively advanced handling, milling, co-firing, and simple renewable energy into solid biofuel. This increases the power density, water resistance, and grindability of biomass while also protecting it from biological degradation, resulting in smooth and competitively priced transportation and storage of torrefied products ^[31]. This

procedure improves the biomass's bodily, chemical, and biochemical composition, allowing it to perform better in covering and gasification applications. Many studies have been conducted to investigate the effect of torrefaction system time and temperature on bodily and chemical composition [49].

Because of the breakdown of OH-corporations during the torrefaction process, the cloth loses its capacity to absorb water and thus remains solid and hydrophobic during storage. Thus unsaturated systems (nonpolar in nature) form which is essential for preserving the torrefied mass against organic degradation. Torrefied biomass can be used as a solid gas for residential or commercial applications. It is also compatible with coal in pulverized coal boilers [50]. For woody biomass torrefaction, a typical mass and strength stability is that 70% of the mass is retained as a strong product containing 90% of the initial strength content. Different 30% of the mass is converted into torrefaction gas which contains only 10% of the energy of the biomass [51].

6 Liquid biofuels for road transportation, commercial aviation and niche markets

The transportation sector faces particularly strong challenges and requires a radical change and long-term policy support to confront the demand for decarbonization. A wide range of alternatives are being investigated, ranging from energy efficiency, overall improvement of vehicle efficiency, engine downsizing, fuel efficiency, hybrid engines, plug-in hybrid vehicles, flex-fuel engine, electric vehicles, fuel cell vehicles (FCVs), etc. [52] The focus of this review is with biomass-based fuels.

Biofuels have been used since the end of the nineteenth century, but they have only gained popularity in the last two or so decades. For example, ethanol consumption increased from approximately 18 billion litres (Bl) in 2000 to 94 Bl in 2014, while biodiesel consumption increased from a few hundred litres to approximately 30 Bl during the same time period (see below). The reason for this is that biofuels, whether blended or neat, offer the best short- to medium-term alternative to fossil fuels, which currently dominate the non-fossil fuel transportation market. Because of the potential implications for land use and food security, this area has also received the most criticism. There are, however, other novel alternatives, including non-biomass being investigated and will be discussed briefly in this review. Figure 19 shows the global production trajectory of biofuels, years 2000 to 2015, which, as can be appreciated, corresponds primarily to ethanol.

Based on current projections, there are numerous biofuel estimates. [53,54,55,57,58,59]

According to Global Industry Analysis Inc. ^[56] global ethanol and biodiesel consumption will more than triple by 2018. Aside from the traditional markets (Brazil and the United States), this report sees Asia-Pacific as the next region with the greatest potential for future growth, with an annual rate of approximately 29% over this period. There are of course many other scenarios (e.g. www.fas.usda.gov, Refs 60–62), all of which come up with different projections. Biofuels in this context refer to fuels produced from any organic matter, either directly from plants or indirectly from industrial, commercial, domestic, or agricultural wastes.

6.1 Bioethanol

As shown in Fig.19 bioethanol has historically been the most important alternative to road transport and will remain to be so throughout the short to medium term. The USA, with 55.5 Bl, and Brazil, with around 27 Bl, are the true giants of bioethanol. Other increasingly important producers are Argentina, China, Colombia, the EU, and Thailand. Estimates range from 3% to 40% of total transportation demand by mid-century.

The development of flex-fuel (or multi-fuel) engines is part of a new ethanol fuel trend in the transport sector. This technology does not represent a revolutionary or fundamental change, but rather a long chain of small improvements with potentially large implications. The flex-fuel engine has been revolutionized in a very short time, with continuous improvements. Notably, these innovations were implemented at a low cost. Flex-fuel engine's flexibility is obvious, with their sophisticated fuel system allowing the simultaneous use of different fuels blended in any proportion, and thus represents new opportunities and challenges for the industry, consumers, and society as a whole, as in the case of Brazil. The Brazilian government is prioritizing research and development investment in order to improve the flex-fuel engine.

6.2 Biodiesel

Biodiesel production also increased rapidly over the past decade e.g. from 2.4 Bl in 2004 to 29.7 Bl in 2014, as seen in Fig. 19 The use of biodiesel has increased significantly in many countries, e.g. Argentina, Brazil, the EU, and the USA, while in many others it is under consideration.

Biodiesel can be used neat (100% or B100), or in various blends, in any diesel engine with little or no modification to the engine or fuel system and does not require new refueling infrastructure. It maintains the same payload capacity and range as conventional diesel and provides similar or slightly reduced horsepower, torque and fuel economy. Biodiesel-like fuels are also being tested for use in aviation to replace jet kerosene, potentially opening up a significant new market (see below). And it is the rapid increase in the use of biofuels in transportation (biodiesel and bioethanol) that has sparked a massive debate about the potential implications for land use and food security, which is covered in the following two sections.

Fig.19. Ethanol, biodiesel, and HVO global production, 2004–2014

6.3 Other biomass-based biofuels and their applications

Various novel alternatives, other than biodiesel and bioethanol, are emerging though it is difficult to make any reliable forecast given the huge uncertainties involved. CNG (compressed natural gas, which includes renewable natural gas, biogas, and Biomethane due to compatibility), bio-gasoline, bio-butanol, hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO), fatty acid methyl ester (FAME), methanol, isobutanol, hydrogen, and syngas are some of the alternatives that offer greater fuel diversification in the transportation sector. The use of diesel-like biofuels in the aviation industry is the most major alternative use being pursued (see the section 'Aviation biofuels'). All of them have great potential at least theoretically but there are many longer-term alternatives that will be considered only briefly.

According to NGV journals, CNG vehicles are widely used in many countries (about 22.5 million worldwide), with China and Iran leading the way with about 4 million each, followed by Pakistan (3.7 million) and Argentina (2.44 million). Despite such impressive numbers, these figures should be interpreted with caution.

7.4. Biogas and biomethane

Biogas, a mixture of methane and carbon dioxide, is the most important gaseous biomass fuel used widely in many parts of the world. Biogas production and application can be divided into three categories: (i) small domestic production and applications; (ii) small cottage industrial applications; and (iii) industrial production/applications. A significant shift in biogas technology in the last 20 years or so has been a shift away from energy alone toward a more 'environmentally friendly technology, which allows the combination of waste disposal with energy and fertilizer production in both developed and developing countries. Thus, the main

driving force in biogas production is not energy, but the necessity of addressing environmental and sanitary problems and hence it is regarded as an environmentally friendly alternative ^[63].

While traditional village-like biogas plants (e.g. in China, India, and Nepal), are declining, the number of new plants is nevertheless growing as many countries now consider the production of biogas from MSW, landfills, waste, etc., a viable alternative for the reasons stated above. Future biogas applications will be primarily for modern rather than traditional uses.

Despite its low calorific value, one advantage of biogas is that it can use existing natural gas distribution systems and can be used in all energy applications designed for natural gas. Currently, one of the most common uses of biogas is in internal combustion engines to generate electricity. It is also compressed for use in light- and heavy-duty vehicles. However, only a few thousand vehicles are thought to be using biogas, e.g. in niche markets such as in rubbish/waste collection trucks, buses, etc.

BIO-METHANE is emerging as an alternative, particularly in Europe (Germany, The Netherlands, Sweden, and Switzerland) where most of the plants are located. It can be obtained via two main routes: (a) by the upgrading of biogas from anaerobic digestion (manure, wet biomass, industrial waste, etc., and solid biomass (energy crops, corn, grasses, etc.); and (b) by the treatment and synthesis and upgrading of gas from the thermo-chemical treatment of solid biomass (wood and wood residues, short rotation coppice (SRC), straw, etc.). This option is still in the demonstration stage, but attracting considerable interest ^[64].

FAME (fatty acid methyl ester) is produced from vegetable oils, animal fats, cooking oil, and wastes by transesterification. Its physical-chemical characteristics are similar to those of mineral diesel. FAME is already an important fuel, e.g. in 2011 global output was about 2.5 Mt (close to 3 Bl) and growing by 16% annually. It is being promoted as an environmentally friendly fuel and any possible impacts on food security and land use are covered in the following two main sections.

HVO (hydrotreated vegetable oils) is a new process, based on oil refining know-how, also used for the production of biofuels for diesel engines. In the process, hydrogen is used to remove oxygen from the triglyceride vegetable oil molecules and to split the triglyceride into three separate chains thus creating hydrocarbons that are similar to existing diesel fuel components. This allows the blending in any desired ratio without any concerns regarding quality ^[65]. It is being promoted as a good and environmentally friendly fuel and could play an important role in the future.

HTL (hydrothermal liquefaction) also known as crude-oil and bio-oil, is a thermal depolymerization process used to convert wet biomass into diesel-like fuels. HTL is actively being investigated as a viable route for converting a vast range of biomass-based materials into liquid fuel, without the need for pre-drying. Upgrading bio-crude improves the physical and

chemical properties to produce a fuel corresponding to diesel or biodiesel. Properties such as viscosity, density, heating value, oxygen, nitrogen, sulphur content, and chemical composition can be modified towards meeting fuel standards using strategies such as solvent extraction, distillation, and catalytic cracking. Although costs are currently high (approx. US\$ 4.44 per gallon gasoline equivalent (GGE), or US\$1.571 per litre, this is expected to fall to around US\$3.03–3.79 per GGE (0.80–1.00 per litre) by 2050 ^[66].

METHANOL fuel, currently produced mostly from natural gas, has been used for decades, though in small quantities. More recently there seems to be a revival of interest in this fuel as many of the previous barriers (technical, economic) are gradually being reduced. It is a particularly attractive alternative in some countries with an abundance of natural gas reserves such as the USA, with lower costs and GHG emissions. The American Methanol Institute (www.methanol.org), a strong advocate, firmly believes methanol has a future as a transportation fuel ^[67].

HYDROGEN is another strong contender, though this is nothing new since it has been used as fuel as far back as the 17th century and was a popular fuel in the 1920s and 1930s. Hydrogen is experiencing a comeback and despite many obstacles (high costs, new infrastructure, etc.) this option is being taken more seriously by enthusiasts and car manufacturers alike though it remains to be seen if hydrogen will seriously take off in the near future.

BIO-BUTANOL offers various advantages of higher energy content, the use of higher blends in unmodified engines, and easy transport (i.e. pipelines). Bio-butanol has a high potential for use in aviation as it has similar characteristics to kerosene. The disadvantage is that production techniques are not yet as advanced as that of the most established biofuels. Nonetheless, there is a growing interest and considerable investment has gone into it but serious hurdles remain.

ISOBUTANOL is actively being tested in various labs around the world because its fuel characteristics are similar to gasoline does not absorb water and is less corrosive than ethanol; mixes well with gasoline and can be transported via pipelines. The first commercial plant commenced in 2012 in the USA using corn to isobutanol but it has almost a quarter less calorific value than gasoline. Additional problems include higher investment capital difficulties in scaling up contamination and lack of industrial experience.

BIO-GASOLINE has also attracted a lot of interest because it is a biomass-based fuel e.g. (grasses, sugarcane pulp, etc.) which can be directly converted into gasoline, using catalysts to convert plant sugars into hydrocarbon molecules very similar to petroleum. It has the advantage of higher blends and energy value; can use gasoline pipelines and it is more efficient than say ethanol. Still it is a long way off from the commercial scale.

SYNGAS, or synthetic gas, can be obtained from many feedstocks (natural gas, coal, biomass, etc.), and is usually a product from gasification whose main application is electricity, although

it is often used as a fuel. However, because it has a low calorific value, added to the fact there are much better and cheaper alternatives, it is unlikely syngas will become an important fuel in the future.

6.4 Aviation biofuels

Civil aviation is a global industry with global issues and challenges that necessitate global solutions. Civil aviation transported 3.3 billion passengers in nearly 100,000 daily flights in 2014 and this figure is expected to double by 2034; it contributed \$2.4 trillion to the global economy and employed approximately 58 million people.⁴⁵ The International Air Transport Association (IATA) predicts commercial aviation to grow annually by 5% until 2030, exceeding expected fuel efficiency improvements by approximately 3%; this implies that fuel consumption and emissions will continue to rise significantly. The combination of increasing passenger demand and fuel costs and pressure to reduce anthropogenic emissions (currently the sector accounts for 2–3% of the total global emissions) has placed the aviation industry under considerable strain. IATA is committed to achieving carbon-neutral growth by 2020 and a 50% reduction by 2050.

For the reasons stated above, the use of biomass-based (bio jet fuels) in commercial aviation has received considerable attention in recent years, as it is currently regarded as one of the best short to medium-term solutions to fuel challenges. Consequently, almost all major commercial airlines, and some military sectors (i.e. USA), are heavily involved in testing and developing biojet fuels. Brazil for example is developing specific national policies aimed at the utilization of biofuels in commercial aviation given the country's favorable conditions and historical experience^[68]. In the USA various companies are investing to produce initially 1.2 billion gallons (4.54 Bl) by 2020.

Given the nature of the high-quality drop-in fuels required in aviation few realistic alternatives exist though there may be many in theory. Because of the high quality of biojet fuels both the feedstock and conversion technology are more complicated and still need considerable R&D efforts. Fisher-Tropsch-fuels (FT) which are still in the development stage and are expected to be commercially available in the early 2020s are the most realistic options. HTL and FAME are both also closed to market introduction^[69]. The availability of feedstocks on a large and sustainable scale is critical to the successful implementation of biojet fuel. Currently, the most economic option is edible oils e.g. palm and soybean oil. Algae, jatropha, camelina sativa, and salicornia bigelivii appear to be the most promising non-edible oily crops for biojet fuel, but only in the long term. Another promising research avenue is the use of lignocellulosic materials and wastes.

The main impediment is still the cost of feedstocks and conversion processes. IATA anticipates that aviation biofuels will become price competitive by the mid-term, in the early 2030s, as a

result of a combination of two main effects: (i) traditional jet fuel price increases (especially when a carbon cost is factored in) and (ii) expected biojet fuel production cost reductions. In any case, this remains a highly uncertain area, particularly with current low oil prices which could impact negatively new R&D.

The evolution in demand for biojet fuel is driven by many factors including growth in air travel, environmental, sustainability, social, political, and regulatory issues; incentives, mandates, and fiscal. The current oil price glut is widely expected to be temporary. Cortez is the Research Coordinator on this report, which has a large number of contributors. Instruments, infrastructure improvements, technical and sustainability, standards for international trade and so on.

It is, therefore, difficult to forecast how this market may develop. Scenarios range from a total demand of 9 EJ year⁻¹ in 2010 to a demand of 16 to 25 EJ year⁻¹ by 2050 (roughly between 375 and 575 Mt respectively). Assuming a 10% blend the potential trade of biojet fuel by the same year will be between 36.8 and 57.5 Mt (or 1.6 and 2.5 EJ) a rather conservative estimate [69].

Biojet fuels have not been a major concern either from an environmental, social, or land use perspective mainly because it is a nascent industry.

7 Use biomass energy in running vehicle

Energy efficiency analysis for different biomass-utilization scenarios would help make more informed decisions for developing future biomass-based transportation systems. Diverse biofuels produced from biomass include cellulosic ethanol, butanol, fatty acid ethyl esters, methane, hydrogen, methanol, dimethyether, Fischer-Tropsch diesel, and bioelectricity; the respective powertrain systems include internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, hybrid electric vehicles based on gasoline or diesel ICEs, hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, sugar fuel cell vehicles (SFCV), and battery electric vehicles (BEV).

Most ethanol is made from corn kernels and sugarcane, but this practice raises heated debate due to competition with food supplies; furthermore, its contribution to the transport sector is minimal or modest. Lignocellulosic biomass is presently believed to be the only major renewable bioresource that can produce a significant fraction of liquid transportation fuels and renewable materials in the future because the overall energy stored in phytobiomass each year is approximately 30-fold of the energy consumed for transportation. But the future role of biomass in the transport sector remains in debate.

A great variety of biofuels can be produced from lignocellulose biomass, including cellulosic ethanol, butanol and/or long chain alcohols, electricity, bioalkanes, fatty

acidesters ,hydrogen hydrocarbons and waxes . The biofuels that will become short-, middle- and long-term transportation fuels is a matter of vigorous debate. Among them, some biofuels may have a particular niche market.

Fig.20. The scheme of energy efficiency analysis for biomass to wheel efficiency

calculation $\eta_{BTW} = \frac{W}{E_B} = \eta_{BTF} * (1 - \eta_{TDL}) * \eta_{FTW}$ [10]

The biomass-to-wheel efficiency , an energy conversion ratio of an automobile's kinetic energy to the harvested and delivered biomass in the front of the door of bio refineries, involves three sequential elements biomass-to-fuel production, fuel transport and distribution, and the powertrain system responsible for the fuel-to-wheel conversion . The BTW efficiency is the lumped efficiency from chemical energy in biomass to kinetic energy for vehicle driving. The η_{BTW} value can be calculated as below ;

$$\eta_{BTW} = \frac{W}{E_B} = \eta_{BTF} * (1 - \eta_{TDL}) * \eta_{FTW}$$

Where W is the kinetic energy transferred to wheels;

E_B Is the chemical combustion energy of the biomass, where dry corn stover as a typical biomass contains ~65% carbohydrates (cellulose and hemicellulose, mainly), ~18% lignin, ~5% ash, ~12% other organic molecules and the E_B value is 16.5 MJ of low heating value/kg of corn stover ;

is the biomass-to-fuel (BTF) efficiency through biorefineries or power stations without significant inputs or outputs of other energy;

is the fuel loss efficiency during its transport and distribution; and

is the fuel-to-wheel (FTW) efficiency from the fuel to kinetic energy through powertrain.

The η_{BTF} value can be calculated as $\eta_{BTF} = E_F / E_B$

where EF is the fuel produced in biorefineries or power stations. The η_{BTF} values of current corn ethanol as a reference range from 46% to 50% , and the value of 49% is chosen as a baseline . Through the biomass sugars platform, potential biofuels include cellulosic ethanol, butanol, fatty acid esters (ester-diesel), hydrogen, and methane. Through syngas made by a thermochemical pathway, potential biofuels are ethanol, hydrogen, methanol, dimethyl ether (DME), FT-diesel, and electricity . Also, electricity can be produced through direct combustion for the generation of steam followed by a steam turbine/generator, or biomass integrated gasification combined cycle (BIGCC) to fuel cells .

7.1 Fuel-to-wheel efficiency (η_{FTW})

Two major internal combustion engines for passenger vehicles are gasoline Otto (spark plug firing) ICE and diesel (compression ignition) ICE. Gasoline ICEs have a low weight-to-power ratio (e.g., ~ 1 g engine per W output) but their maximum efficiencies are relatively low, approximately 32%, due to low compression ratios . In contrast, diesel ICEs have a higher weight-to-power ratio (e.g., ~ 3 – 4 g engine per W output) and a much higher energy conversion efficiency, more than 40% . It is reasonable that diesel ICEs are widely used in heavy-duty trucks, tanks, and tractors. In Europe, diesel ICE passenger vehicles are more popular mainly due to higher fuel costs and more climate change concerns. Audi A3 vehicles based on ICE-diesel have 35.4 miles per gallon of diesel, higher than ICE-gasoline (24.7 miles per gallon of gasoline) , suggesting a $\sim 26\%$ enhancement in η_{FTW} efficiency. (Note: the volumetric energy density of diesel is ~ 13 – 14% higher than that of gasoline).

Practical η_{FTW} values of ICEs are much lower than their maximum efficiency because of (i) the engines operate at $\sim 70\%$ of their maximum efficiency during most driving conditions, (ii) $\sim 17\%$ loss for engine idling, (iii) $\sim 2\%$ consumption for accessories (e.g., air conditioning, lighting), and (iv) $\sim 25\%$ loss in transmission . Therefore, the η_{FTW} for ethanol-ICE is approximately 14% as a baseline and this value would be improved through higher compression rate ethanol engine and better transmission . Advanced diesel vehicles are expected to have η_{FTW} values of 20–24% ; the value of 23% is used in this study.

Hybrid electric vehicles (HEV) can eliminate idling losses, allow a small engine to work at nearly optimal conditions, and utilize braking energy with regenerative braking . Therefore, advanced HEV-gas is estimated to have η_{FTW} values of 29–34% . Similarly, the η_{FTW} values of HEV-diesel can be increased to 32–38%, with a preferred value of 37%.

The hydrogen fuel cell vehicle (FCV) is a complicated powertrain system involving compressed hydrogen, PEM fuel cells, an electric motor, and a rechargeable battery . FCVs feature zero tailpipe pollution and high energy conversion efficiencies due to PEM fuel cells, whose theoretical energy efficiency from hydrogen to electricity is up to 83%. As a result, many companies have attempted big research FCV projects, and some of them produced

prototype FCVs, such as the GM Sequel, the BMW Hydrogen 7, the Ford Focus FCV-Fuel Cell, the Toyota Fine X, and the Honda FCX Clarity. The η_{FTW} values of FCVs range from 41 to 54%, with a mean value of 45%. SFCVs based on FCVs would have an on-board bioreformer that can convert the sugar slurry to high-purity hydrogen and absorb waste heat from PEM fuel cells. Because the efficiency of sugar-to-hydrogen is 107% based on low heating value the η_{FTW} value for SFCV is estimated to be 48% with a range of 44–57%.

Battery electric vehicles (BEV) have the highest η_{FTW} values, although they still have some energy losses in battery recharging and release, storage loss, motor, and so on. BEVs have predicted η_{FTW} values from 64 to 86%, with a mean value of 68%.

Fig.21. Comparison of fuel-to-wheel (FTW) efficiency for different powertrain systems.

7.2 Biomass-to-Wheel (BTW) efficiency (η_{BTW})

A combination of 12 kinds of biofuel production approaches and 6 kinds of advanced powertrains for passenger vehicles results in more than 20 scenarios. In this analysis, 14 scenarios were calculated. The current corn ethanol/ICE scenario has η_{BTW} value of ~7%, i.e., only 7% of the chemical energy in corn kernels is converted to the kinetic energy on wheels, implying a great potential in increasing biomass utilization efficiency. An ethanol HEV-gas system would double η_{BTW} values to 14–18%, suggesting the importance of developing hybrid electric vehicles based on available liquid fuel distribution system. There is no significant difference in η_{BTW} between butanol and ethanol, but butanol may have other important future applications, such as powering jet planes. The η_{BTW} values of methane/HEV-gas and methanol/HEV-gas are 19% and 17%, respectively, higher than those of ethanol and butanol, mainly due to higher product yields. Since ICE-diesel has higher η_{BTW} efficiencies than ICE-gas, the scenarios based on HEV-diesel through DME and FT-diesel (except ester-diesel) would have higher η_{BTW} values than HEV-gas scenarios. For ester-diesel, a significant amount of energy is lost during aerobic fermentation due to thermodynamic and bioenergetic limits resulting in low η_{BTW} values. Even for the niche jet fuels market, the production of ester-

diesel through semi-aerobic microbial fermentation might not be competitive with anaerobic butanol fermentation and a high-energy-retaining efficiency hybrid of biocatalysis and chemical catalysis.

Fig.22. Comparison of biomass-to-wheel (BTW) efficiency for different biomass utilization scenarios.

Although (hydrogen) fuel cell vehicles (FCVs) have higher η_{BTW} efficiencies than ICE-gas and ICE-diesel, the H2/FCV scenario shows $\sim 46\%$ and $\sim 15\%$ η_{BTW} enhancements over ethanol HEV-gas and DME HEV-diesel, respectively, because significant energy loss in hydrogen distribution discounts FCV's advantages over HEV-diesel. The sugar/SFCV scenario would have very high η_{BTW} values of approximately 27% due to lower energy consumption in fuel transport and heat recapture in the sugar-to-hydrogen biotransformation, compared to the H2/FCV scenario.

BEV scenarios are among the highest η_{BTW} values, from 20% to 28%, with increasing electricity generation efficiencies from direct combustion BIGCC to FC-power.

In the long term, SFCVs will likely win over BEVs due to advantageous energy storage densities, safety, infrastructure, and environmental impacts. The great potentials for increasing η_{BTW} values from ethanol-ICE to the future systems (HEV and SFCV) suggest that more efficient utilization of biomass would greatly decrease greenhouse gas emissions, and biomass use could result in more benefits to the environment, rural economy, and national security than originally expected. Through SFCVs, about $\sim 7\%$ of annual US biomass resources may be sufficient to meet 100% of US light-duty transportation fuel needs in the future.

8 Challenges and Future of bio-fuel

8.1 Direct land use change (DLUC), indirect land use changes (ILUC) and biofuels production

DLUC and ILUC were hardly an issue a few years back. The rapid expansion of biofuels in particular detonated a growing concern with land use and food security. The debate accelerated significantly after the publications of Fargione et al.^[70] and Searchinger^[71] from which a large body of literature has emerged ^[72-79]. In summary, early studies failed to present a realistic picture due to the complexity of the factors involved and a lack of scientifically supporting data. The methods employed were overly simplistic, insufficient and overestimated the potential impacts of biofuels on land use. For example, the spike in food prices blamed primarily on biofuels in 2007/08 was later shown to be unfounded because prices fell significantly at a time when biofuels production continued to rise significantly. This resulted in overreaction and poor policy decisions, particularly by the EU. Many of the early findings have been challenged as new data is being added particularly ILUC. According to the European Biofuels Technology Platform (EBTP), 'ILUC emissions cannot be observed or measured but must instead be modelled.' Many of the options considered, in most cases, will not help to fight ILUC impacts, but merely penalize the biofuels industry without bringing any sustainability benefits.

Brown and Brown^[80] challenged the Searchinger et al.^[70] theory on ILUC regarding the negative impacts caused by USA corn-based ethanol production. They emphasized the lack of evidence that ethanol production is causing deforestation in other parts of the world. This viewpoint was bolstered further by Dumortier et al.^[81], who contend that ethanol production has lower environmental impacts than previously presented.

The emerging consensus seems to indicate that the potential impacts of ILUC are far lower than originally stated by many early studies; because of its diverse and complex nature, which might hardly reflect (perhaps distort) the real impacts of land use change caused by biofuels. Of course, given the broad range of potential impacts posed by both DLUC and ILUC, many uncertainties remain. The ILUC methodology in particular requires significant enhancement.

8.2 Land use in biofuel production

It should not come as any surprise that estimates of land use for biofuel production also vary widely depending on the source and assumptions. Estimates range from 40 Mha to 800 Mha. FAO data shows that by 2050, 72 Mha of additional land will be needed to meet additional food demand (45% would be for food, 40% for livestock feed). FAO data also suggests that 700-800 Mha of land may be available for growing energy crops which is an optimistic

assumption; CCC8 suggests a range of 100 to 700 Mha. Much will depend on how agriculture develops in the future as well as the reduction of massive food waste. It is inconceivable that the agricultural sector would not be completely transformed and modernized in order to meet the numerous challenges as doing so would be impossible in its current form, particularly in many DLGs.

Ravindranath et al.^[82] analysed crop land requirement for liquid biofuels on a crop-by-crop basis whereby the land use requirement is based on 100% substitution of projected demands for biodiesel and bioethanol to 2030. Sugarcane yields 24 Mha of bioethanol, sweet sorghum yields 39 Mha and maize yields 50 Mha. The range for biodiesel is 29 Mha for palm oil or 106 Mha for jatropha to 221 Mha for soybean.

In the case of Europe (potentially the largest importer of biomass energy) the Gallagher Review^[83] estimated that between 22 and 31.5 Mha of additional land would be required within the EU to meet 2020 biofuels needs and between 13 and 19 Mha would be required outside the EU. This assumes that 60% of European biofuel consumption will be imported by 2020. A rather small amount is unlikely to generate any significant impact.

It seems therefore almost impossible to provide any reliable estimates at this point. There is some agreement, however, that land in and of itself is meaningless unless the debate includes the potential for increasing crop productivity, the nature of biofuels, energy, resources, technological, social, and economic developments, massive food waste^[84,85] and so forth.

8.3 Food versus fuel and food and biofuel from outright opposition to pragmatism

This subject has been extensively discussed, and there is a substantial body of literature available^[86,87]. The biofuel debate has taken two main forms, media and academic, embracing two main and conflicting schools of thought: (i) the anti-biofuels lobby; and (ii) the pro-biofuels lobby^[88]. Food security (prices) and land use competition have been particularly contentious issues. For example an FAO report^[89] stated that biofuels were responsible for 3% to 30% of food price increase from 2002–2008, which turned out to be wrong and FAO was forced to rectify later on. It is a clear example of jumping to conclusions without sufficient supporting evidence, perhaps for ethical/moral bias rather than science. Figure 23 demonstrates the debunking between biofuel production and crop and commodity prices. It clearly shows that, while biofuel production increased rapidly, major crop and commodity prices fell dramatically. The effects of biofuel development on food prices have been debated extensively^[90-92].

The food versus fuel debate began in the United States and then spread to the European Union. Because of the existence of strong pro and anti biofuels lobbies, large-scale corn use, the powerful farmers lobby, and other vested interest groups, corn use in the United States has been

the subject of a vigorous (still ongoing) political debate. The intensity of this debate in both the EU and the US can be explained in part by the existence of specific policies designed to subsidize the widespread use of biofuels.

Much of the criticism leveled at biofuels has centered on "first-generation" (G1) technologies, at least until second-generation (G2) technologies become more widely available. Another major issue has been the media's overemphasis on a few feedstocks (maize, sugarcane, and cereals), as well as the overall negative impact.

The EU has played a critical role in ensuring bioenergy/biofuel sustainability, in part because the European Commission is acutely aware of the social, environmental, and policy implications of large-scale biomass energy imports.

In Brazil bioethanol is not perceived as a problem because the country has a large agricultural area and sugarcane (the source of ethanol) is an exceptionally good feedstock. In contrast, biofuel production in Brazil has been accompanied by increased food production. Except for China, most other countries do not debate this issue; in fact, most countries see the expansion of biomass energy as an opportunity rather than a threat if produced and used sustainably. As a result there is no universally held perception on the aspect.

As a consequence, are we witnessing the end of a sterile debate over food versus biofuels? Probably not, especially in the United States, due to vested interests, the complexity of biofuels and the difficulty of enforcing sustainability criteria legislation in many parts of the world. What is becoming increasingly clear is that, when produced and used sustainably, biofuels and food production can be complementary. The emerging consensus suggests that the debate should shift from 'food versus biofuels' to 'food and biofuels.' This growing acquiescence is based on a better understanding of the pros and cons of biomass energy a recognition that the underlying causes affecting food security, prices, hunger, and so on are numerous and diverse and that on balance the benefits outweigh the negative impacts when produced and used sustainably.

Fig.23. Global crop commodity prices and the aggregated price of all commodities versus global biofuels.

8.4 Environment, sustainability, energy balance and subsidies GHG/environment impacts

Climate change is one of the most serious challenges that humanity is currently facing. Biomass energy has been widely promoted as a partial solution to GHG problems and perhaps the pro-biomass lobby in particular was too optimistic and overstated the overall environmental benefits. What role, then, can biomass energy play in limiting GHG emissions? The answer is dependent on the specific feedstock^[93]. Each crop has its benefits and drawbacks and needs to be assessed on its merit.

For ethanol the highest GHG savings are recorded for sugar cane from 70% to more than 100%.^[94,95] whereas corn can save up to 60% but may also cause 5% more GHG emissions^[96], although there remain strong disagreements. For example, in a recent study^[97] the authors identified a 354 Mt CO₂equi. reduction from ethanol since 2008 much greater than expected as a result of technological improvements in grain ethanol production greater use of advanced low-carbon biofuels and the rising carbon intensity of petroleum fuels. Some G1 biofuel crops provide net GHG benefits only under certain conditions, such as using abandoned or degraded lands (no DLUC or ILUC) utilizing co-products implementing sustainable production practices (excluding the use of nitrogenous fertilizers), and so on^[98].

So, where do we stand now? On a life cycle analysis basis, it appears safe to say that biofuels in particular provide a net GHG benefit (30-100% compared to petroleum fuels) when co-products are used and GHG emissions from land conversion are excluded. Negative GHG savings i.e. increased emissions, may result in particular when production takes place on converted natural land and the associated mobilisation of carbon stocks is accounted for. These findings, however, are constantly being challenged as new data comes to light.

Furthermore, while the focus has been on biomass energy, new evidence is emerging, demonstrating that livestock is responsible for a significant portion of GHG emissions, e.g. Goodland and Anhang⁷⁹ estimated it at about 32.56 Gt year⁻¹ of CO₂e or about 51% of global CO₂. A more recent FAO⁸⁰ study calculated it to be 7.1 Gt in 2013, or 14.5% of human-induced GHG. Whatever the final figure might turn out to be, the implication is that replacing livestock products will be an even better strategy to combat climate change. Finally, GHG impacts are influenced by a wide range of variables, with considerable room for disagreement.

8.5 Global subsidies

Another contentious issue, particularly for fossil fuels and nuclear energy, that is rarely presented in a balanced way. Depending on how the term "subsidy" is defined and calculated, estimates range from US\$550 billion per year to US\$5.6 trillion per year (International Monetary Fund). This is various orders of magnitude greater than biofuels. As things stand,

this is a very unequal playing field that tempers the development of alternative energy sources, energy efficiency, and conservation, primarily in oil-producing countries. Again, it is now widely acknowledged that biofuel subsidies play a minor role when compared to say oil.

8.6 Energy balance

As with subsidies, this is none the less a tricky complex area given the diverse nature of both mineral oil and biomass (energy content, physical and chemical characteristics, etc.). The point this paper is trying to convey is that the energy balance of biofuels has often been portrayed as negative without rigorous comparative analysis.

Biodiesel balances for rapeseed and soybean feedstocks range from 1 to 4, whereas palm oil is around 9. Balances for crop-based ethanol range from less than 2 for maize to around 2-9 for sugar cane (8 to 10 in Brazil). Sugar-cane-based ethanol produced in Brazil is dependent not only on feedstock productivity, but also on the fact that it is processed with biomass residues from sugar cane (bagasse) as an energy input. Cellulosic feedstocks have even higher energy balances.

Given the complex web of economic, technical, and political factors, the energy balance is frequently oversimplified. Different assumptions and calculations frequently result in different results. The energy balance is not static, but changes continuously and require constant data updating. Further research is still required to improve our understanding so that decisions are made in a more balanced way. None the less, it should be remarked that some agreement is emerging on the overall positive energy balance for several biofuels, though divergences will persevere due to the diverse nature of energy sources both fossil and renewable.

8.7 Sustainability

It is at the core of biomass energy and it is safe to say that considerable advances have been made e.g. in any biomass energy project sustainability has become a fundamental component, a far cry from the early days. It was the Brundtland Report in 1987 that put sustainability on a global footing. There is extensive and burgeoning literature for residues, biomass energy plantations (forestry and crops), and multi-functional systems such as agroforestry.

However, because many regions have limited resources, the development of an international biomass energy trade will be uneven around the world. Biomass energy trade offers a real opportunity to export primarily to developed countries for some developing countries endowed with large biomass resources and lower costs. This type of trade is unlikely to play a significant role in countries with limited biomass resources.

In the short to medium term, the most promising areas for international trade are (i) densified biomass (pellets, torrefied wood, wood chips) for combined heat and power and co-firing in

coal power plants and small to medium-sized applications, (ii) biofuels (biodiesel and ethanol for use in road transport), and (iii) charcoal (for use in restaurants), though this market will remain comparatively small.

Biofuels in particular is growing rapidly as they have considerable potential for substituting oil in the transportation sector, given the right conditions. The international ethanol trade fluctuates substantially from year to year. Annually, between 3 and 5 billion litres of fuel ethanol are traded with Brazil and the United States being the main exporters and Japan and the European Union being the main importers. However, this is expected to rise dramatically as international demand rises, with over 40 countries interested in ethanol fuel alone. One of the major constraints is that few countries, with the exception of Brazil and a few others can supply both their expanding domestic market and international demand. Another factor that may postpone new investment at least in the short term is a glut in oil prices.

The long-term viability of large-scale international biomass energy trade must be dependent on environmentally sustainable production. This necessitates the creation of criteria, project guidelines, and certification systems, all of which must be supported by international bodies. This is especially important in markets that rely heavily on consumer opinion, as is currently the case in the EU. There are still significant barriers to the development of international trade. There is also a growing concern about the rapid expansion of this market. For example, in the USA the media has been reporting the potential destruction of local forests used for pellets production primarily exported to Europe, despite good intentions. Thus, should biomass energy trade be treated differently from any other commodity? Or should market forces be left to determine supply and demand as any other commodity? A key concern must be to ensure its sustainability.

Unlike fossil fuels, biomass energy has hardly been traded regionally, nationally, and, even less so, internationally. Most trading has occurred at a local level, but this is now changing and is becoming an important international trading commodity, particularly densified biomass (i.e. pellets and chips) and liquid biofuels (i.e. ethanol and biodiesel). This rapidly evolving market is difficult to predict, but current trends indicate that major developments will emerge, owing to growing international interest (political, technical and economic)^[99].

For example, Kranzl et al.^[100] examined the perspectives and potential implications of international bioenergy trade by evaluating a large number of studies. In all scenarios, the volume of biomass energy traded internationally increases significantly. In the ambitious scenario, for example, 14-26% of biomass energy demand is traded between regions in 2030; solid biomass trade ranges between 700 and 2500 Mt. These values for 2050 are 14-30% trade biomass, with solid biomass responsible for 800 to 4200 Mt.

9 Conclusion

Because of the potential benefits, many developed and developing countries consistently support biofuel production. This research aims at the perspectives of third- and fourth-generation biofuels in terms of long-term sustainability. The following are some of the study's key findings.

First-generation and second-generation biofuels are associated with greenhouse gas emissions, environmental impact, habitat loss, community conflicts, and significant production costs. The use of edible biomass in first-generation biofuels sparked widespread concern. It competes with global food demands, limiting production to a few countries. The high investment costs and low efficiency of converting feedstocks to biofuels are the other constraints. Second-generation biofuel production is constrained. In terms of environmental and social impact, both the first and second generations have advantages and disadvantages. This means that both generations will be unable to meet the increasing demand for biofuels and energy transition goals shortly.

Third- and fourth-generation biofuel development has far-reaching implications for global socio-economic growth and sustainability goals. It helps to maintain carbon equilibrium, biodiversity conservation, sustainable water use, air quality, soil conservation, and social enterprise sustainability.

Many companies are investing considerably in biofuels to accelerate the global energy transition. It will become increasingly important to develop and implement sustainable biofuel standards, and more entrepreneurs and businesses will commit to believing that the benefits will outweigh the risks.

Nanotechnology has the potential to enable the development of next-generation biofuels. By incorporating nanomaterials into the development process, the efficiency of biofuels can be greatly increased. Magnetic nanoparticles, carbon nanotubes, metal oxide nanoparticles, and other Nano catalysts have the potential to become critical components of long-term bioenergy production. However, the majority of yield data are based on small-scale biofuel production. Further research is required to investigate the effectiveness of nanotechnologies in the pilot production of biofuels.

The production of natural bio-products like proteins, pigments, fatty acids, and bioplastics by macro- and microalgal biofuels aids in the development of a circular economy. As a result, algae-based green and bioeconomy opportunities include a new supply chain in manufacturing, cleaner fuel, food security, and GHG mitigation benefits.

It is reasonable to assume that third- and fourth-generation biofuels will become more alluring for international commercial use in light of technological advancements, extensive research, and development.

Third- and fourth-generation biofuels can be realistically used as a transition approach if specific sustainability requirements are met. Nature-inspired solutions have tremendous potential as a sustainable energy source for our planet in the future.

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